

IMAGE SECURITY IMPLEMENTATION IN SOCIAL MEDIA

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ABSTRACT

One of the most challenging issues in data sharing systems is the enforcement of access policies and the support of policies updates. Cipher text policy attribute-based encryption is becoming a promising cryptographic solution to this issue. Cipher text – Attribute Based Encryption scheme enables an encryptor to define the attribute set over a universe of attributes that a decryptor needs to possess in order to decrypt the cipher text, and enforce it on the contents. Thus, each user with a different set of attributes is allowed to decrypt different pieces of data per the security policy. It is proposed to use scheme to improve security and efficiency in attribute based multimedia data sharing. The proposed multimedia data sharing system includes Key Generation Center, Data Owner, Data User, Data Storing Center system entities that helps to share image securely using scheme. Here, specifically focus is on sharing image in 'jpg' format.

KEYWORDS: Image Secret sharing Encryption Chaotic theory Linear independence